

“CAN I HAVE A CUP OF TEA?”

(mavzusida ingliz tili fanidan 4-sinflar uchun tayyorlagan Isoatlik dars ishlanma)

Go`zalxon Masharipova

Xonqa tumanidagi 49-ayrim fanlar chuqur o`rganiladigan davlat ixtisoslashtirilgan umumta`lim maktabining ingliz tili fani o`qituvchisi

Lesson plan

Theme: Can I have a cup of tea?

AIMS:-To learn how to ask for a drink or food

Developing :-to enable pupils to ask for a drink or food

Socio-cultural:-to raise awareness of how children in Great Britain celebrate birthday

Vocabulary: A glass of water, a bowl of salad, a cup of tea, a spoon, a spoon, a knife,

Required equipment: the computer, cards, pictures, water, juice and salad

The process of the lesson.

1.Greeting. (5 minutes) 2.Checking home task. (5 minutes) 3.Presentation a new theme. (20minutes) 4.Consolidation. (10 minutes) 5.Conclusion. (5 minutes)

The course of the lesson: 1.Greeting. (5 min)

Teacher: Good morning pupils! **Pupils:** Good morning! **Teacher:** How are you? **Pupils:** We are ok! **Teacher:** ok. Sit down, please

Teacher: What lesson is it now?

Pupils: English

Teacher: Ok, now, if you are ready shall I begin our lesson?.After greeting I write the date on the blackboard.

Teacher: What date is it today? **Pupils:** Today is the _____

Teacher: Let’s speak about the weather a bit today. Could you tell me what season is it now?

Pupils: Autumn.

Teacher: What’s the weather like today?

Pupils: It’s sunny and warm

And now physical exercises. Sing the song “are you sleeping? Yes I am ”.

Teacher: Play the DVD. Dear pupils let’s sing the song along with the DVD altogether, pupils stand up and begin

DVD script:

Are you playing? yes I am

Watch me doing and do the same

Shake your head and comb your hair
Count to three and find your pair
Are you playing? yes I am
Watch me doing and do the same
Wiggle fingers and wiggle mouth
Clap your hands

II Checking homework (5 min)

Teacher: Thank you, well done and now I’ll check your homework and mark your. And let’s play game snowball with answer the questions.

what’s the weather like in summer?

What’s the weather like in winter?

What’s the weather like in December?

What’s the weather like in January?

III Presentation a new theme (20 min)

Activity1. Ok well done and now our new topic. Our new topic is about “Can I have a cup of tea?”

Translate this sentence in Uzbek please. Bir choshka choy ichsam bo’ladimi?

And now play game. “Can I have a cup of tea?” or “Can I have a glass of juice?” one pupil come to the blackboard. You are host and you are guests. You are one by one come to the blackboard and ask this question. Can I have a cup of tea? And you are answer this question and practice. Do you understand?

Pupils: yes

Teacher: Ok let’s begin

Activity2. well done and now our new words. Look listen and repeat.

A glass of water- bir stakan suv A bowl of salad – bir kosa salat

A glass of juice- bir stakan sharbat A cup of tea – bir choshka choy

A spoon-qoshiq A knife – pichoq

- Your home task to learn by heart the new words.

Activity3. First revise the Present Continuous Tense if necessary. Ask: “ What are you doing?” And help the pupils answer in the present continuous tense. Eg. “I’m sitting”, “we are listening”, “Soxiba is drowing”. etc.

NOUN+VERB+ING

IV.Conclusion. (10 minutes)

- Activity4.** And now this exercises is about read and match.

V Conclusion (5 min)

Teacher: Dear pupils the lesson is over. I will give small gifts to all of you. And now I’ll give you homework for the next lesson.

Homework: to learn by heart the new words

Ok my dear pupils the lesson is over Good bye. Thank you for attention.